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SOLAR COLLECTOR FOR WATER SOFTENING USING NATURAL COMPONENTS

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Annotation. *In this article, you can soften water using the natural method. For preliminary softening of water, we need to design and manufacture a stationary plant using solar energy for heating. For softened water, we used the ashes of cotton stalks and leaves of the "Gujum" tree.*

Key words: *water softening, hard water, solar collector, ash, ash filling neck, battery, regulated, cotton stalks and leaves of the Gujum tree.*

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СОЛНЕЧНЫЙ КОЛЛЕКТОР ДЛЯ УМЯГЧЕНИЯ ВОДЫ С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ КОМПОНЕНТОВ.

Аннотация. *В данной статье приведены можно умягчения воды по натунальной способой. Для предварительного умягчения воды нами необходимо спроектирована и изготовлена стационарная установка с использованием солнечной энергии для подогрева. Для умягченной воды нами была использована зола стеблей хлопчетника и листья дерева "Гужум".*

Ключевые слова: *умягчения вода, жесткая вода, Солнечный коллекторб, золы, горловина для засипки золы, батарея, регулированныи чток, стеблей хлопчетника и листья дерева "Гужум",*

For preliminary softening of water, we have designed and manufactured a stationary plant using solar energy for heating. Fig.1. The main element of the installation are; standard flat steel heating radiators, dimensions 1400x560 mm, capacity 1 pc. 6 l. Each battery is covered with cellophane film. The installation is assembled from 6 pieces of such batteries at an angle of 45-50°c. This angle is adjustable with a stem. The basis is pipes Ø 75-100 mm. At ambient temperatures of 25°c and above, the body and base of the unit also turn into a heating element[1]..

Water for heating is supplied from the tank, passes through the top and drains through the tap into the tank for collecting water.

Tanks of the OVH7 installation can serve as containers.

When performing the whole system, the valve opens, the valve is in the closed position. To determine the heating time, experiments were carried out

with the installation of the "Kagan" in place. The results of the experiments are shown in Figure 2. The temperature of the water in the batteries rises for 1 hour, and then stabilizes. At an ambient temperature of 24.5°C, the water in the batteries

Figure.1. We use a solar collector for heating and softening water for the cooling system in MTP.

1-Tank for non-softened water. 2-neck for sifting ash. 3- bases. 4 - batteries. 5 - tank for non-softened water. 6 - regulated what.

Figure.2. Dependence of the water temperature in the wave collector on the duration of heating.

Ambient air temperature $t_{ok} = 18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 2- Ambient air temperature $t_{ok} = 24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 3- Ambient air temperature $t_{ok} = 35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. heats up to 70°C water temperature at the beater inlet is 21°C.

Vegetation ash is an effective agent for softening hard water. For this purpose, we used the ashes of cotton stalks and leaves of the Gujum tree. The ash can be poured through the mouth of the upper part of the unit or directly into the water collection tank. In the water collection tank, the water should stand for 0.5 hour and then be used for the cooling system. The daily productivity of the installation is 324 liters at an ambient temperature of 15-25°C, -450-550 liters at an ambient temperature above 25°C.

Cotton ash is available to almost every tractor driver, free of charge, non-toxic. The effectiveness of the use of cotton stalks ash mainly comes down to the quantitative assessment of this preparation[2,3]..

We have conducted studies to determine the rational specific consumption of ash per 1 liter of water of different hardness, the effect of water temperature on its softening with ash. The water used for the engine cooling system has an average hardness of 25-30 mg. equiv./l

The experiments were carried out with water hardness of 25 mg. equiv/l and 30 mg. equiv/l. water in MTII department 2, state farm "Kagan" at a water

temperature of 45 °c and 80 °c, time - 0.5 hours, the dose of ash was as follows: 1 g per 1 liter of water, 2 g/l., 5 g /l., 15 g/l., 20 g/l., 30 g/l.

The obtained results of the experimenters are presented in fig. 3.

Figure.3. Changes in water hardness with the addition of cotton stalks ash (initial water hardness 25 mg)

1-At water temperature current = 45 °c, 2-At water temperature current = 80 °c,

REFERENCES

1. Kozlov Yu. S. "Cleaning cars during repairs" M. Transport. 1982. 151s
2. Kuznetsev Yu. S. "Electrizable of automotive fuels" M. MADI. 1978.60s
3. Yakubovich, A.I. Cooling systems for tractor and car engines. Design, theory, design: Monograph / A.I. Yakubovich, G.M. Kukharenek, V.E. Tarasenko. - Minsk: BNTU, 2011. - 435 p.
4. Жураев Т. Х. и др. Решение краевой задачи построения плоских сопряжений геометрическим моделированием для направляющих поверхностей рабочих органов //Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве. – 2020. – С. 346-348.
5. [Shavkat Imomov](#); [Dilorom Ubaydullayeva](#); [Tulkin Abdukurimov](#); [Mukhriddin Fayzullayev](#) Constructive geometric modeling the double sided moldboard bodies for bidirectional rotary plows <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0181766>
6. A.B.Babamuradov, Sh J.Imomov, A.A.Jurayev, S.S.Orziyev, U.F.Khusenov, D.U.Ruziqulova // The importance of seedling cultivation and the device for preparing pots from biohumus in seedling cultivation // The Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology / <https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/2582-4686>
7. Sh.J.Imomov, M.F.Mamatov, A.A.Jo'rayev, S.S. Orziyev , O'F.Husanov // Ko'chat yetishtirishda ishlatiladigan biogumus tuvakchalarining namligini aniqlash bo'yicha laboratoriya tadqiqotlarining natijalari // Agro ilm – O'zbekiston qishloq va suv xo'jaligi /Maxsus son (3) [96], 2023 ISSN 2091-5616
8. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
9. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2024). БОҒЛАРНИ ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШДА ТУПРОҚ-ГРУНТ НАМЛАНИШ КОНТУРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ УСЛУБИ. IMRAS, 7(2), 34-38.
10. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 3(8), 30-32.
11. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. Экономика,

и социум, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.

12. AZ, S. Z. S. N. S. (2020). Analysis of the work on improving the design of dryers inside the ginning plants and the mode of drying.

13. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. E Conference Zone, 61–69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>

14. Ochilovich, S. Z. (2020, September). Inoyatov Ikrom Shaxriloyevich, Shodiyev Ne'matjon Sadirovich. Tabiiy yaylovlar va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati. In Эффе́ктивность применение инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве» международная научно-практическая онлайн-конференция (pp. 25-26).

15. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF THE MESH SURFACE ON THE SEED COTTON DURING THE SEPARATION OF COTTON FROM THE AIR STREAM. In Эффе́ктивность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 121-122).

16. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). KEY FACTORS FOR INCLUSION IN THE EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN IN THE CXM SEPARATOR AND THEIR IDENTIFICATION. In Эффе́ктивность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 119-121).

17. Musinovich, S. M. (2023, June). DRIP IRRIGATION INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS AND SEASONAL WATER CONSUMPTION. In Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 8-14).

18. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.

19. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G'O'ZA O'SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>

20. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o'g'li, S. F. (2022). BUG 'DOY O 'SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO 'JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.

21. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO'RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA'SIRI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>

22. Khudaev, I. J., & Shoximardanova, N. S. (2023). FEATURES OF DRIP IRRIGATION OF CROPS. *PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS*, 2(24), 157-160.

23. Худаев, И. Ж., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2023). ҚОВУН ПОЛИЗ ЭКИНИНИНГ БИОЛОГИК ВА МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 479-482).

24. J.Sh.Fazliev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>

25. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKLANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>

26. Fazliyev, Z. S., Shokhimardonova, N. S., Sobirov, F. T., Ravshanov, U. K., & Baratov, S. S. (2014). Technology of the drip irrigation use in gardens and vineyards. *The Way of Science*, 56.